

A STUDY ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS SAMSUNG MOBILE

Ms Neha Kaushal

Asst.Professor,
Institute of Engineering &Technology Alwar (Raj.)

Dr O P Pathak

Head,Department of Management studies,
Institute of Engineering &Technology Alwar (Raj.)

ABSTRACT

All of us are consumers. We consume things of daily use, we also consume and buy these products according to our needs, preferences and buying power. what we buy, how we buy, where and when we buy,in how much quantity we buy depends on our perception, self-concept, social and cultural background. while buying, we also consider whether to buy or not to buy and, from which source or seller to buy. In some societies, there is a lot of affluence and these societies can afford to buy in greater quantities and at shorter intervals. in poor societies, the consumer can barely meet his barest needs. In order to develop a framework for the study consumer behavior it is helpful to begin by considering the evolution of the field of consumer research and the different paradigms of thought that have influenced the discipline. It is argued that consumer behavior itself emerged as a distinct field of study during the 1960s; and is characterized by two broad paradigms, the positivist and the non-positivist. The positivist paradigm, which is still the dominant paradigm, emphasizes the supremacy of human reason and that there is a single, objective truth that can be discovered by science. The opposing, non-positivist paradigm, envelops the interpretive and postmodern perspectives, which have emerged more recently during the period post-1980 to date. The rational view and the ideology of a homogenous social culture and thereby deny the complex social and cultural world in which consumers live. The objective of non-positivist research endeavor is to achieve a better understanding of consumer behaviorwith no specific intent to influence consumer processes. This article aims to identify different streams of thought that could guide future consumer research.

Keywords: consumer buying behavior, consumer research, conventional, attitudinal, situational.

Introduction: in general terms “consumer is a person who consumes”, especially an individual belonging to a particular gender, age, sex, religion etc. And who acquires Goods or services for direct use or ownership rather than for resale or use in production and manufacturing. In other words, it can be said that the consumer is an individual who buys products or services for personal use and not for resale or reproduce. A consumer is an important person who can make the decision to purchase an item from a particular store, and can be swayed by marketing and advertisements.

A consumer’s buyer behavior is influenced by four major factors such as cultural, social, personal and psychological factors. These factors cause consumers to develop product and brand preferences. Although many of these factors cannot be directly controlled by marketers, understanding of their impact is essential as marketing mix strategies can be developed to appeal to the preferences of the target market. When purchasing any product, a consumer goes through a decision process. This process consists of up to

five stages: problem recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchase decision, post purchase behavior.

The main focus of analyzing consumer buying behavior is to identify, buyers reactions towards Samsung’s marketing strategy that has a great impact on the firm’s success, the marketing concept stresses that a firm should create a marketing mix that satisfies (gives utility to) customers, need to analyse that what, where, When and how consumers buy and needs to predict, how consumers will respond to marketing strategies.

Consumer buying behaviour is the process involved when individuals or groups select, use, or dispose products, services, ideas or experiences (exchange) to satisfy needs and desires. Consumer behaviour is the scientific learning of how people buy, what they prefer to buy, when they need to buy and why they buy i.e. The reason to buy. It mingles elements from psychology, anthropology, sociology, and economics. It makes an effort to understand the buyer decision processes or the buyer decision making process, both individually and in groups. It examines special characteristics of individual consumers such as demographics, psychographics, and behavioural variables in an attempt to understand the needs of the people. It also tries to assess influences on the consumer with the help of groups such as family, friends, reference groups, and society as a whole.

The factors that influence consumer buying behaviour in general are:

- Motivation and participation of consumers in purchasing a specific product.
- Consumer’s attitude.
- Personality and self concept of any individual consumer.
- Ability to remember i.e. learning and memorizing power of the consumer.
- The channel or way through which information processing takes place.

The most common external influences or factors are:

- Cultural influences- influences of culture of the individual buyer
- Sub-cultural influences
- Social class influences – influences related to the individual buyers specific society, religion etc.
- Social group influences – the social group in which individual buyer resides
- Influences the buying behaviour.
- Family influences – it is also an important influences usually observed in various consumers.
- Personal influences
- Other influences

A survey has shown that many elements contribute to make it more difficult in finding consumer’s buying behaviour. The elements are:

- Lack of knowledge of the market.
- Lack of brand awareness and external motivators.
- Lack of satisfaction level of customers.
- Lack of awareness about the perception & expectations of the customers

Market share of Samsung in India:

Indian Smartphone Market Share by Vendor, Q2 2016

Source: IDC Asia/Pacific Quarterly Mobile Phone Tracker Q2 2016

Note – Lenovo Group includes Lenovo and Motorola

Indian smart phone market				
Market shares Q4 2016, Q4 2015				
Region	Q4 2016		Q4 2015	
	shipments (m)	% share	shipments (m)	% share
Total	28.1	100%	27.0	100%
Samsung	6.2	22%	7.0	25%
Xiaomi	3.0	11%	0.9	3%
Oppo	2.6	9%	0.2	1%
Lenovo	2.6	9%	3.0	11%
Vivo	2.1	7%	0.3	1%
Others	11.6	41%	15.6	59%

Source: Canalys estimates, © Canalys 2017
 Note: Where applicable, a vendor's shipment numbers exclude rebranded products for which they

Review of research and development:

Mr. Durra mansoor in his investigation "shopper conduct is the investigation of the procedures that people or gatherings go together in settling on their buy decisions so as to fulfill their requirements". It is significant to specify that the shopper conduct is a mix of client's purchasing mindfulness joined with outside

Helpers to bring about an adjustment in the shopper's behaviour.nesbitt(1959) calls attention to that "brilliant clients don't influence their shopping to list ahead of time since they will look for advancements

and have a tendency to acquire more advantages from them to build their obtaining power".mr.g.shaniesh in his examination "purchasing conduct in a business advertise is portrayed by long process durations, collective choice making, members from various practical regions and levels and once in a while disparate goals, and changing parts of the members amid the purchasing cycle".

Objectives of the study:

- To find out the factors influencing to purchase ratio of Samsung mobile.
- To find out the demand of samsung mobile.
- To study the awareness of samsung mobile users.
- To find out the level of satisfaction towards Samsung mobile.
- To study the problems faced by the customers Samsung mobile .

Methodology:

In this study, an extensive use of both primary and secondary data was collected, descriptive research was used.

Data collection:

An extensive use of both primary and secondary data was collected. The primary data was collected from the samsung mobile users. The information was gathered through structured questionnaire method. The secondary data was collected from journals, magazines and websites.

Sample design:

There are number of Samsung mobile users. The researchers have approached respondents in Samsung showroom to collect the data. For collecting the information, the respondents were chosen by non-probability random sampling.

Scope of the study:

The present study is confined to erode district and considers only various Models of samsung handset. Though the main objective of the study is to analyse customer preference in Samsung handset and the factors influencing them to purchase a particular model, the scope of the study extends to the following related aspects viz., the socio economic characteristics of the respondents, the awareness of Samsung handset users, level of satisfaction towards Samsung mobile and the problems faced by the customer.

Tools of data collection:

by virtue of mass data obtained from the research survey as well as data collected from secondary sources, descriptive research was considered as most appropriate one for the study. The research problems and the questionnaire were all framed accordingly. The core of the study being "a consumer buying behaviour towards Samsung mobile" is to mainly find out the factors influencing the consumer to buy the samsung mobile. These factors were studied through percentage analysis, garret ranking method, chi-square test and anova.

Conclusion

The researcher had made an effort to find out the level of buying behavior of Samsung mobile and it is clear that the public have high awareness on Samsung services. Samsung mobile services attract people because of its quality, model, price, services and memory capacity in Samsung mobile. Hence it is concluded that if the Samsung mobile has come out with effective advertisement it may highly influence the consumer to purchase Samsung mobile.

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